

Fragebogen

1 Sprachenauswahl

**In welcher Sprache möchten Sie den Fragebogen ausfüllen?
In which language would you prefer to fill in the survey?**

Dies ist eine Pflichtfrage, bitte entscheiden Sie sich für eine Sprache.
This is a mandatory question, please select one of the following language versions.

- Deutsch
- Englisch

2 Willkommen

Survey publishing processes

Dear Researchers,

Thank you for taking part in this survey about your publishing processes. Publishing is an important part of our work. Publication processes can be very time-consuming and bureaucratic hurdles can add to this problem. The survey aims to identify interfaces between the various stakeholders within the publishing process and possible points of contact for service providers.

The survey is part of a master's thesis at TH Köln. Answers will be handled in accordance with applicable data protection guidelines, in order to avoid conclusions to be drawn about individual participants.

If you are interested in the survey's results, please feel free to contact me at:
umfrage-publikationsprozess@fraunhofer.de

Please note the following information:

- The participation in the survey is voluntary.
- The participation in the survey can be interrupted at any time and can be continued or discontinued at a later time.
- The survey exclusively serves the purpose stated in the introductory text or e-mail.
- The data will only be evaluated by persons who are obliged to maintain data confidentiality in accordance with § 5 BDSG or confidentiality in accordance with the organizational directive 2018/03/VB/O "Data Protection Measures in the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft", Annex 4/ who are obliged to maintain confidentiality in accordance with the contract for order processing.
- Insofar as personal data is collected, the data subjects are entitled to rights pursuant to the GDPR, including the right to information, correction, revocation or blocking/deletion of the data as well as the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority. The technical and organisational requirements pursuant to Art. 25 and 32 GDPR for the protection of personal data are complied with.
- Under no circumstances will personal data be passed on to other employees of the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft or to third parties not entrusted with the evaluation.

If you have any questions regarding data protection or technical problems, please contact the following persons:
Data Protection Officer of the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft: ralph.harter@zv.fraunhofer.de
In case of technical problems please contact: c9-befragungen@fraunhofer.de

Note: Please expand the window to maximum screen size.

Click on "**Next**" or "**Back**" at the end of a page - please do not use the backwards/forwards function of your browser.

3 Demographischer Teil

Demographic part

At which research institution are you or were you employed during the last five years?

mandatory question, multiple answers possible

- Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft
- Helmholtz Association of German Research Centers
- Max Planck Society
- Leibniz Association
- Other non-university institution, namely:

Please select your employment status. I am employed as...

mandatory question, multiple answers possible

- Student assistant
- PhD student
- Research assistant without management function

Research assistant with management function

Head of institute

Visiting scholar

International visiting scholar

Other:

What is your academic degree?

Bachelor's degree

Master's degree without Intention to do a doctorate

Master's degree with Intention to do a doctorate

PhD

Unsure whether to pursue a doctorate later on

Which gender do you identify with?

Male

Female

Diverse

Not specified

How old are you?

< 20

21-30

31-40

41-50

51-60

> 61

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Which academic field does your research belong?

mandatory question, multiple answers possible

Physics

Engineering (mechanical and production engineering)

Biology

Chemistry

Medicine

Systems and electrical engineering, process engineering

Law

Civil Engineering/Architecture

Materials Science/Materials Engineering

Computer Science

Social Sciences

Economics

Pedagogy

Media, Communication & Marketing

Geosciences

Other:

Do you consider your research fundamental research or applied research?

Fundamental research Applied research

You have indicated that you are employed as an international visiting scholar. Would you tell us which country you are from?

Publication Behavior

Why are you normally publishing?

Please rank the reasons in order of importance. Starting from the top very important to less important.

	1	2	3	4	5
Mandatory publication at the end of the project	<input type="radio"/>				
Requirements of my institution for (internal) performance evaluation	<input type="radio"/>				
Requirements due to my doctoral work	<input type="radio"/>				
In order to enhance my reputation	<input type="radio"/>				
In order to exchange research results	<input type="radio"/>				
External presentation/marketing	<input type="radio"/>				
Acquisition	<input type="radio"/>				
In order to save my research results	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

Other reasons for publication:

In general, the publication process can be divided into 4 parts:

- The **preparation**
- **The research itself**
- **The marketing**
- **The dissemination (dissemination)**

During which of these 4 processes would you like to receive more help, for example in the rendition of services?

multiple answers possible

- Research preparation (literature research, research collaborations, funding, research data management,...)
- Scientific writing (laboratory and research work, writing the scientific paper, etc.)
- Marketing for my work (communication with publishers, secondary publication, license management,...)
- Dissemination of my work (secondary publication, reporting to research funders, academia, social media such as ResearchGate)
- I do not need any support

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How many publications in the following types of documents do you author on an annual average?

	> 5	2-4	1	0
Articles in scientific journals with peer review	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research articles without peer review	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conference proceedings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Book chapters	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Books	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
'Grey literature' (literature that was not published by publisher.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Poster/Lecture	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Which audiences are your publications aimed at?

multiple answers possible

- Scientists of your academic field
- Scientists of related academic fields
- Individuals and groups within certain sectors of industry (i.e. emphasis on applied sciences)
- Interested laymen
- Other:

Are your publications also aimed at international scientists?

Yes, also at international scientists **No**, international scientists do not belong to my target group

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In your opinion, what are the most important criteria for selecting a suitable publication medium?

multiple answers possible

- International distribution
- Specialization
- Reputation of the journal
- Impact factor of the journal e.g. frequency of quotation
- Quality of peer review of submitted articles
- Speed of publication of submitted articles
- Long-term availability
- Publication cost for the author/institution
- Amount of royalty for the author
- Open access availability
- Other:

How are you supported by your supervisor during the publishing process?

multiple answers possible

- Regular communication
- Joint research/laboratory work
- Financially
- He/she co-writes the text
- Internal review
- I must list him/her as a co-author
- I receive very little support
- Other:

How do you support your staff during the publishing process?

multiple answers

- By sharing my expertise
- In an advisory capacity
- I assist in researching
- Financially
- I contribute to the writing process
- I review the finished work (internal review)
- I hardly have time to support my team members
- Other:

If you are uncertain about which journal to publish your research results in, who are you asking?

Mehrfachnennung möglich

- Colleagues
- Supervisor(s)
- Library staff
- I prefer to do my own research in which journal to publish in
- Other:

7.1.1 Filter - Ich recherchiere lieber selbst

You have indicated that you research for suitable journals by yourself. Would you tell us which sources you are using for your research? (For example, subject databases, library catalogs, Google)

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A system which supports you during the publishing process is being planned. Where do you personally see the greatest need for support during the publication process?

**Are you aware of the second publication right? **

By clicking on the question mark icon, you will find an info text about the second publication right.

- Yes, I have heard of it
- Yes, I have used it before
- No

8.1.1 Filter, wenn ja

How do or how would you publish your scientific results a second time, if possible? (second publication law)

multiple answers possible

- In the institutional repository
- On my own website
- In subject repositories
- On social media (e.g. ResearchGate,...)
- Other:

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How often do you publish in connection with externally funded projects?

- Very frequently
- Frequently
- Rarely
- Very rarely
- Not at all

9.1.1 Filter

Which project funding agencies do you work with most often?

Drag and drop the boxes to the right into your order (only the ones you are working with).

1 2 3 4 5 6

BMBF	<input type="radio"/>					
DFG	<input type="radio"/>					
BMWi	<input type="radio"/>					
EU	<input type="radio"/>					
State funding (e.g. NRW, Bavaria,...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Other	<input type="radio"/>					

Please list the other project funding agencies.

Are you aware of the funding requirements of the funding agencies you have selected?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Do you publish your publications via open access?

- Yes
- I choose open access for some of my publications
- No

10.1.1 Filter - ja**Please rate the criteria below according to how important they are in your decision whether to publish open access or not?**

	Very important	Important	Partly important	Rather unimportant	Unimportant
Quick availability	<input type="radio"/>				
Better reusability through free licenses	<input type="radio"/>				
Visibility beyond your own specialist community	<input type="radio"/>				
Worldwide availability	<input type="radio"/>				
Higher citation frequency	<input type="radio"/>				
Support of the Open Access idea	<input type="radio"/>				
Long-term availability of publications better guaranteed	<input type="radio"/>				
Corporate strategy (Open Access policy)	<input type="radio"/>				
Increased visibility and findability on the internet	<input type="radio"/>				
Requirements of the research sponsors (third-party funds)	<input type="radio"/>				
Departmental strategy	<input type="radio"/>				
Other: <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

10.2.1 Filter - nein**What are the reasons why you do not publish Open Access?**

multiple answers possible

- I do not know what exactly open access is
- I do not know potential advantages of open access publishing
- I am not sure what the legal implications of open access publishing are
- If I publish my results open access, I feel like they will not get enough credit
- It is too much effort for me to obtain information on copyright and usage rights
- I do not receive any remuneration for my work
- There is a lack of information and support services concerning open access publishing
- There is a lack of qualitative open access journals in my field of expertise
- The publication costs for open access publications are too high for me
- Other:

Publishing agreements define the rights of the author and the publisher in scientific publishing, for example in journals. Does your institution have guidelines on how to deal with a publishing agreement?

multiple answers possible

- Signature policy
- Archiving
- Allocation of rights
- There are no guidelines
- I am not aware of any specifications
- Other:

How do you secure funding for your publications?

multiple answers possible

- I plan for funding from the beginning of my project
- My institution/employer is funding the cost
- I use publication funds
- I try to avoid any cost and publish only in journals, which are free of charge
- Other:

Do you also disseminate your scientific contributions/data via social networks?

multiple answers possible

- ResearchGate
- LinkedIn
- Academia.eu
- Xing
- Twitter
- Other:
- No

Do you participate in peer review processes?

- Yes, I review the following number of publications annually:
- No

Are you aware of portals of publishers or external service providers that support you during the publishing process?

- Yes, namely:
- No

Some academic fields are beginning to use informal publication sources (e.g., blogs, etc.). How do you evaluate the use of these sources?

- I have no opinion on this
- I see the following advantages:
- I am critical about the use of informal media because

Are informal publications accepted in your professional community?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

You have reached the end of the survey.

If necessary, review your answers now and then click on " **Submit**" to finish your questionnaire.
Once sent, you cannot make any changes.

I would like to thank you very much for giving me a moment of your time and participating in this survey. The results of the survey will become part of the author's master's thesis and can be made available if interested after the survey is completed.

If you have any questions or suggestions, please feel free to contact me at:

umfrage-publikationsprozess@fraunhofer.de

Thank your for your participation.

